

Psychological Behavioral Changes in School Going Children during Online Classes in Covid Lockdown

Dr. M K Sharma ¹, Meeta Joshi ²

¹. Professor , Faculty of Computer Applications and Technology , Amrapali Group Institute , Haldwani – India

². Research Scholar , Shri Venkateshwara University

Abstract:- In the Year 2019 , corona virus pandemic effected the way of learning and schooling of themajority of population of school going children . During Covid time lots of psychological effects identified among children and most of them were negative . There are very few research carried out to check impact of psychological effects during online study . The present paper aimed to find and compare the some very important psychological and behavioral changes associated with lockdown effects on children from three district of Uttarakhand (Nainital , Almora and Udham Singh Nagar) . Parents of 480 children and school going children including boys and girls participated in the study. An online survey using Google forms and 1 sampling techniques was conducted during 25 days between March and April 2020, representing the early phase of the lockdown period because of COVID. Parents and children asked to answer questionnaires about general information , changed reading and learning habits , some important psychological responses like anxiety, change in mood, sleeping , change in food habits . Massive use of mobile screens, disturbed physical activity, and lack of playing sports before and during the lockdown .

Keywords:- COVID-19, Psychological Symptoms, Behavioral Symptoms, Child Habits, Housing Conditions, Online Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Owing to the corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19), schools were unexpectedly and abruptly closed in many countries during lockdown and thereafter also . The period of the school closure varied by region; however, school going children were requested to remain at home and have restricted contact with class mates and friends . Given this unusual school closure with these severe restrictions, children's lives were more severely affected than by conventional annual closures [1]. These unusual conditions prompted us to investigate how this school closure affected schoolchildren. Studies have revealed that COVID-19 school closures exerted profound negative impacts on school children physically [2] and psychologically [3]; however, so far, no extensive study has been conducted of the precise mechanisms affecting children's mental health.

II. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

For this paper our research work was driven by the following research questions:

- 1) Change in physical and mental health problems in school going children , during online classes because of school closure in lockdown .
- 2) Some identified factors closely associated with children experiencing these problems . Our paper hypothesis is a finding , a relationship between increased mobile screen time and some other factors . We also assessed the internet connection problem in rural areas . The survey form included questions about changed sleep habits, food habits and change of behaviour because of school closure and long duration stay at home .

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A semi structured , open ended online survey form (using Google Forms) and offline study was conducted with 500 school children in three districts of Uttarakhand, including public and government schools. Parents and students filled the given questionnaire in which we enquired about general information , changed reading and learning habits , some important psychological responses like anxiety, change in mood, sleeping , change in food habits. Correlation and logistic regression method were used to find out the relationships between physiological, psychological and behavioral change problems.

IV. MEASURES AND DATA ANALYSIS

The survey was constructed initially in English and Hindi, for this study and that included multiple choice questions with rating scale questions. The final version was tested on 8 schools and with children aged 8–18 years per districts in Uttarakhand . Comprehension was adequate, and no changes were required in the survey.

All calculations were performed using SPSS 26; the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to find out normality of the data. Given the lack of normality in the continuous variables, non-parametric tests were used. Ordinal alpha, which is considered the most appropriate for ordinal items, is calculated. Kruskal-Wallis tests were performed to compare continuous variables across 3 different districts and Chi-squared tests were used to compare proportions across the different groups.

Spearman correlations were calculated to analyze the relationship between continuous variables included in the hierarchical regression analyses. To test the association between “anxiety,” “mood change,” “sleeping habits change,” “behavioral alterations,” “food habits change,” during lockdown .

V. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

Online class environment during lockdown phase in India and closures of school for a long duration negatively impacted school children physically and psychologically. Screen time on laptop or Mobile phone was associated with both physical and mental health status. Therefore, children should not be engaged more in online during . There is a great need of offline schooling and other activities for school going children to again setup their daily routines.

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